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eQATOR

Horizon Europe EU project

Electrically heated catalytic reforming reactors

Grant Agreement No. 101058293

Deliverable Report

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Executive Summary

A Communication and Dissemination Kit for the ēQATOR project, so that consortium partners can communicate about the project in a uniform way and contribute to establishing a strong and visually appealing project identity, has been developed. The kit contains branding elements such as the project logo, promotional materials, templates and guidelines and an online presence through the creation of a website and accounts in social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn). This Deliverable gives an overview of the kit content.

The branding material has already been shared with the ēQATOR project partners, ensuring that they all have access to it and that standardised communication is built in favour of the project. ēQATOR online elements include the knowledge and competence of the partners, and a communication channel between SEZ and the rest of the consortium has been established in order to allow a general agreement in regard to content that will be promoted on the internet.

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1 Introduction

A communication and dissemination kit for the ēQATOR project has been developed, consisting of a branding kit and an online presence kit. Consideration of the consortium partners' needs, requests and suggestions allowed an identity kit to be built in a cooperative manner. Both the branding and online presence kits are meant to be used by all consortium partners.

The branding kit consists of these elements:

- Project logo with variations in colour and inclusion of slogan
- Project identity images (gradient bar and icons)
- Project Poster
- Project Flyer
- Template for internal and external material

The online presence kit consists of these elements.

- Website
- Social Media accounts

2 Branding kit

2.1 Project logo

A project logo was developed based on the inputs and feedback of the consortium. The logo consists of the project's name, a visual element which crosses the project's name, and optionally the project slogan depending on the space available. The visual element is composed of an electric cord and a plug. The colour scheme with the dominant colours blue, red and green alludes to electricity, heat and renewable energy, respectively.

Different variations of the logo are available depending on the background colour and space available. All the logo variations are shown in Figure 1. The colour scheme for each part of the logo is in Figure 2.

Figure 1. eQATOR logos with different colour schemes and backgrounds. The logo on the top left is the primary logo with complete colourful gradient logo with slogan. The logo on the top right is the plain colour version. The next two are the black colour version (left) and white color version (right). The remaining logos have the same colour scheme, but without the slogan.

e	R: 26 G: 118 B: 194	#1a76c2	ATOR	R: 38 G: 198 B: 132	#26c684
	Q	R: 224 G: 41 B: 49		#e02931	

Figure 2. Colour scheme for each part of the logo

2.2 Project Identity images

Project identity images for the use of consortium partners have also been developed, specifically

- Gradient bar with the project colours, shown in Figure 3
- Icons for project objectives, innovations and key impacts, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Gradient bar depicting the project colour scheme.

Figure 4. Icons for project objectives, innovations and key impacts.

2.3 Project poster and flyer

Partners will organise and participate at various events in the frame of the project. For this purpose, adequate visual representation is necessary. Therefore, a poster and a flyer were developed that includes these elements:

- The project logo
- Partner logos
- Short project description
- Short description of challenges, solutions, objectives and impacts
- EU funding acknowledgement
- Link to the project website and social media channels

The poster is in Appendix 1 and the flyer in Appendix 2.

2.4 Template for internal and external materials

Templates were created for the production of text documents (Deliverables and Milestone Reports) and powerpoint presentations. These are contained in Deliverable D.1.3 Internal communication tools.

2.5 Guidelines for the project identity

To assist the partners with dissemination activities, a presentation for the consortium partners outlining the guidelines on how to use the project identity, including how to acknowledge EU funding properly, has been created. This information will ensure that the formal aspects of the communication activities will be consistent throughout the project.

The guidelines entail the following points and can be found in Appendix 3:

- Project logo basic and variations, related guidelines (including colour codes) and where to find them
- Project identity images and where to find them
- EU funding acknowledgement
- Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission responsibility

- Social media accounts and tags
- Applications for IPR protection of results

3 Online presence kit

3.1 Website

A [website \(www.eqator.eu\)](http://www.eqator.eu) was created where the project identity, colours and logo are presented across all pages. The website has the purpose to inform a broad audience about the project's objectives and impacts, as well as providing access to the project's updates (called "news") and events. The goal of the website is to raise awareness, so the website also provides an invitation to the visitor to subscribe to a newsletter and connect with the project social media accounts. The website enjoys a simple and short name which should make the website easy to remember, share and access. The website homepage is shown in Figure 5.

Other parts of the website are shown in Appendix 4.

Figure 5. ēQATOR website homepage.

3.2 Social media accounts

Accounts in the social media channels [Twitter](https://twitter.com) and [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/) have been created. ēQATOR's online presence makes usage of its short and simple name in these social media platforms. The project's Twitter account homepage is shown in Figure 6, and its LinkedIn homepage is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. ēQATOR Twitter account homepage.

Figure 7. ēQATOR LinkedIn account homepage.

4 Conclusions

A comprehensive communication and dissemination kit that ensures visually appealing and consistent communication of the ēQATOR project has been created. The kit is designed to draw attention to the ēQATOR project and increase brand recognition across different types of channels both traditional and online. The kit thus includes a set of branding identifiers (logo with colour scheme, identity images, poster and flyer) and an online presence (website, Twitter and LinkedIn).

Guidelines for the use of the project identity kit have been created

All kit elements are uploaded in the project repository (ēQATOR SharePoint), so that all consortium partners can have access to it at any time and from anywhere.

Appendix 1 – ēQATOR poster

CONTEXT

Methanol is produced from syngas, the product of the steam reforming of methane, a chemical reaction that requires a large amount of heat. This heat is usually generated by the combustion of fossil fuels and accounts for about 10% of the CO₂ emissions in the chemical sector.

ēQATOR proposes a **paradigm change** to the heating of catalytic reactions based on renewable energy. Through its **lower energy intensity and processing footprint**, the ēQATOR technology will achieve a **cost-competitive renewable methanol production** with near zero CO₂ emissions, accelerating the transition to the next generation of intensified catalytic processes for the EU industry and beyond.

OBJECTIVE

ēQATOR aims to develop **scalable, electrically-heated catalytic reactor technologies** that will allow **conversion of biogas into syngas** with **improved efficiency** compared to the state-of-art. Focusing on dry-reforming, it utilizes both the CO₂ and the methane from biogas, which bridges biogas production with downstream conversion technology into higher-added value products such as methanol, fuels and hydrogen.

MAIN INNOVATIONS

ēQATOR provides an **integrated development of catalysts and reactors**, and **two different, complementary, electrical heating technologies**:

- **microwave heating**.

Through these separate technologies, ēQATOR will lead to a **disruptive electrically-heated reactor technology** for syngas production.

This translates into **up to 90% size reduction of total reactor unit** and **50-75% reduction in catalyst volume**.

UNIQUENESS

KEY IMPACTS

- **Reduction of CO₂ emissions by 60-80%** when compared to current processes.
- **Higher conversion per pass, improved heat management, higher energy efficiency** and better carbon utilisation and atom economy, in **more compact reactors**, using renewable carbon feedstock.
- **Strong industrial commitment** to build a large deployment of catalytic process electrification, through an economically viable, local, smaller-scale methanol production from biogas.
- **Novel optimised catalysts and reactor designs** for biogas valorisation to methanol.

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Appendix 2 – eQATOR flyer

Key Impacts

eQATOR provides an integrated development of catalysts and reactors, and two different, complementary, electrical heating technologies:

- microwave heating

These technologies translate into:

- Reduction of CO₂ emissions by 60-80% when compared to current processes.
- Higher conversion per pass, improved heat management, higher energy efficiency and better carbon utilisation and atom economy, in more compact reactors, using renewable carbon feedstock
- Strong industrial commitment to build a large deployment of catalytic process electrification, through an economically-viable, local, smaller-scale methanol production from biogas.
- Novel optimised catalysts and reactor designs for biogas valorisation to methanol

eQATOR Partners

Get involved!

- @eqator.eu
- @eqator
- www.eqator.eu
- contact@eqator.eu

eQATOR

Electrically Heated Reactors

BUILDING SCALABLE, ELECTRICALLY-HEATED CATALYTIC REACTOR TECHNOLOGIES THAT WILL ALLOW CONVERSION OF BIOGAS INTO SYNGAS

eQATOR – Electrically heated catalytic reforming reactors – has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101058293.

Challenges and Project Vision

Methanol is produced from syngas, the product of the steam reforming of methane, a chemical reaction that requires a large amount of heat. This heat is usually generated by the combustion of fossil fuels and accounts for about 10% of the CO₂ emissions in the chemical sector.

eQATOR's revolutionary and sustainable technology will initiate a paradigm change to heating technologies based on renewable energy.

eQATOR aims to change this scenario!

Conventional Heating

Electric Heating

Objective

eQATOR aims to develop scalable, electrically-heated catalytic reactor technologies that will allow conversion of biogas into syngas with improved efficiency compared to the state-of-art. Focusing on dry-reforming, it utilizes both the CO and the methane from biogas, which bridges biogas production with downstream conversion technology into higher-added value products such as methanol, fuels and hydrogen.

Uniqueness of eQATOR approach

- Novel optimised catalytic and reactor design for biogas valorisation in methanol
- Reduction in CO₂ emissions up to 80% and up to 40% and compared to current processes
- Consideration of sustainability and environmental friendliness
- Strong industrial commitment to catalytic process electrification

Mission

eQATOR proposes a paradigm change to the heating of catalytic reactions based on renewable energy. Through its lower energy intensity and processing footprint, the eQATOR technology will achieve a cost-competitive renewable methanol production with near zero CO₂ emissions, accelerating the transition to the next generation of intensified catalytic processes for the EU industry and beyond.

eQATOR – Answering the need to shift from fired- to electrically-heated catalytic reactors for greening industry and contributing to European energy challenges

Current use of fired-heated processes with large CO₂ emissions

Large amount of biogas available, not utilized for chemicals' production

Large demand of greener platform molecules, such as renewable methanol

TRL6 demonstration (10m³/h biogas -> 10kg/h methanol, 1000h running) of electrically-heated dry reforming for the synthesis of methanol from biogas in decentralised modular units

• 60-80% decrease in CO₂ footprint
• >90% decrease in reactor size

```

            Biogas (CH4+CO2) --> Electrically-heated dry reforming --> Syngas (mixture of CO and H2) --> Methanol synthesis --> Methanol (CH3OH)
            
```

No management of the CO₂ present in the biogas today

Innovation 1: Tailor-made catalysts for optimising the products' ratio, maximising the yield and fitting with the new reactor design

Innovation 2: Optimised reactor design for efficient electrical heating

Innovation 3: Optimised global process design for efficient integration of up and downstream processes and operation with optimal energy efficiency and product yield in a cost-effective manner

Platform molecule for different applications

Versatility to other feedstocks and reactions

Appendix 3 – Guidelines for project identity

eQATOR guidelines for the project identity

- Project logo and guidelines (incl. colour code) 2
- Project identity images 3
- EU funding acknowledgement – official documents 4
- EU funding acknowledgement – EU emblem 5
- EU emblem – rules for use 6
- Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission responsibility 7
- Online presence (website and social media) 8
- Applications for IPR protection of results 9

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1

Project logo and guidelines (incl. colour codes)

Where to find them?

- Guidelines: [HERE](#)
- Logo: [HERE](#)

e	R: 26 G: 118 B: 194	#1a76c2
Q	R: 224 G: 41 B: 49	#e02931
ATOR	R: 38 G: 198 B: 132	#26c684
	R: 5 G: 124 B: 60	#057c3c

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2

Project identity images

You can find them [HERE](#)

- Icons for the project key impacts

MAIN INNOVATIONS

eQATOR provides an **integrated development of catalysts and reactors**, and two different, complementary, electrical heating technologies: **microwave heating**.

Through these separate technologies, eQATOR will lead to a disruptive electrically heated reactor technology for syngas production.

This translates into up to **90% size reduction of total reactor unit** and **50-75% reduction in catalyst volume**.

KEY IMPACTS

- **Reduction of CO2 emissions** by 60-80% when compared to current processes.
- **Higher conversion per pass**, improved heat management, **higher energy efficiency** and better carbon utilisation and atom economy, in **more compact reactors**, using renewable carbon feedstock.
- **Strong industrial commitment** to build a large deployment of catalytic process electrification, through an economically-viable, local, smaller-scale methanol production from biogas.
- **Novel optimised catalysts** and reactor designs for biogas valorisation to methanol.

- Gradient bar with the project colours

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EU funding acknowledgement – official documents

- [Article 17 of the Grant Agreement](#)
- [Graphics guide to the European emblem;](#)
- [Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027;](#)
- [Communication and visibility rules for EU funding programmes 2021-2027 – Guidance for Member States.](#)

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EU funding acknowledgement – EU emblem

Any project communication or dissemination of results must include:

Funded by
the European Union

or

Funded by the
European Union

The EU emblem can be downloaded here: [European Flag \(europa.eu\)](http://European Flag (europa.eu))

Any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must include:

Funded by
the European Union

or

Funded by the
European Union

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

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5

EU Emblem Funded by the European Union

The minimum height of the EU emblem must be 1 cm. For specific items, like pens, the emblem can be reproduced in a smaller size. When using the EU funding statement in a small size, we highly recommend using the horizontal version.

- Do not choose a font other than Arial, Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu or Verdana.
- Do not use any font effects
- Do not add other graphic elements between the EU emblem and the text
- Do not make the text disproportionately bigger or smaller compared to the EU emblem
- Do not modify the text proportions.
- Do not use any colour other than Reflex blue, white or black.
- Do not write 'EU'. It must always be spelled out as 'European'
- Do not write in all capital letters
- Do not replace the EU emblem with the European Commission logo.
- Do not replace the EU emblem with any other graphic element.
- Do not modify the EU emblem.**
- Do not add the name of the programme to the funding statement.
- Do not write the name of the programme in conjunction with the EU emblem.
- Do not add a graphical element with the name of the EU programme

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6

Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and the Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Please use one of the following texts:

"eQATOR - Electrically heated catalytic reforming reactors (Grant Agreement No 101058293). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting agency can be held responsible for them."

OR

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

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Online presence (website and social media)

Please remember to tag eQATOR

- In your LinkedIn posts: [@eQATOR](#)
- In your Tweets: [@eQATOR](#)

Also do not hesitate to also tag:

- Sintef as coordinator (on LinkedIn and on Twitter)
- SEZ and EBA as communication and dissemination leaders
(SEZ: [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#). EBA: [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#))

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8

Applications for IPR protection of results

Applications for protection of results (including patent applications) filed by or on behalf of a beneficiary must — unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible — include EU funding acknowledgement.

Please use the following text:

The project ēQATOR leading to this application has been funded by the European Union under the grant agreement No 101058293.

 Funded by the European Union

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Appendix 4 – Other parts of the ēQATOR website

News section

The screenshot shows the 'News' section of the ēQATOR website. The header is green with the word 'News' in white. Below the header, it says 'Follow the latest developments of the project!'. There are two news items displayed as cards with a green background and a white photo on the left.

News
Follow the latest developments of the project!

5 days ago
ēQATOR's partner meeting at IFEU's office in Heidelberg on 16-17/11/2022

Oct 6
First kick-off meeting took place at SINTEF's office in Oslo on 14-15/06/2022

Bottom part with an invitation to the newsletter subscription and the EU acknowledgement

The screenshot shows the bottom part of the ēQATOR website, featuring a newsletter subscription form and an EU acknowledgement section. The background is grey.

Subscribe to Our Newsletter

Interested to learn more about the latest developments of the ēQATOR Project? Sign up for our newsletter to get the latest news and updates directly in your inbox.

Enter your email here *

*By signing up for our newsletter, you accept our [privacy policy](#).

[Sign Up](#)

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